

DELVING INTO NOTE-TAKING TECHNIQUE IN CONSECUTIVE INTERPRETING

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of the process of note-taking in consecutive interpretation in students and how efficient it is depending on the individual. The focus of this report is on note-taking technique which is believed to be a major one in consecutive interpreting training based on the interpreting studies literature. Note taking is a technique for interpreters to support their short-term memory when reformulating the original speech. It is essential to understand that the interpreter's notes are not everything, they are a support for the memory, but it is not recommendable for the interpreter to rely exclusively on their notes.

Key words: consecutive interpreting, note-taking, abbreviation.

Introduction. Interpreting is regarded as a translational activity, as a special form of translation. "Within the conceptual structure of Translation, interpreting can be distinguished from other types of translational activity most succinctly by its immediacy" Pöchhacker (2004, p.10). Interpreting may be classified, labeled and divided into types and subtypes based on various criteria. When categorizing according to mode, two major types of interpreting emerge: simultaneous and consecutive interpreting. Note-taking (NT2) is a distinctive feature of consecutive interpreting (CI), in particular 'classic' consecutive where systematic note-taking is used (Pöchhacker 2004, p. 19) According to Gile's Effort Model (1997), notetaking is considered as an intermediate step bridging the gap between information encoding and decoding in the process of consecutive interpreting. Stenzl (2002) also identifies note-taking as a coding process from which interpreters can put the source language into the interpreting context. Among the written notes, words, symbols and signs serve as 'codes' for interpreters for further interpretation at the later stage.

Consecutive interpreting is one of the three modes that go to make up what we call conference interpreting. It involves listening to what someone has to say and then, when they have finished speaking, reproducing the same message in another language. The speech may be anything between a minute and twenty minutes in length, and the interpreter relies on a combination of notes, memory and general knowledge to recreate his or her version of the original. Gile (1995, p. 178) believes that note-taking is critical for consecutive interpreting in

terms of requirements of note-taking while maintaining the efficiency of notes as memory cognitive capacity, and the key lies in “how to reduce processing capacity and time reinforces”. Siantova (2015) defines note-taking as a memory pillar and stimulation of intellectual activity as it is not possible for human memory to keep in completeness a large communication for longer time. Therefore, efficient notetaking is one of the most important skills trainee interpreters have to learn.

Literature review. Consecutive interpreting is a versatile form of verbal translation between languages. With or without taking notes, an interpreter begins to deliver messages in a target language when a speaker pauses his/her speech or conversation. Taking notes simply means quickly writing down information as a record or reminder.

However, note-taking might be compared with a move in chess; to understand how to make the move is quite easy, but to master it in order to create a winning combination of the move and the others is a hard and demanding job. Note-taking in consecutive interpreting is a skill to be learned. There is no abstract theory about the skill, but there are a wide range of practical principles laid down by succeeding generations of consecutive interpreters over time. These principles have been made of both empirical studies digging deep into nearly every aspect of the skill and research books elaborating main theoretical approaches to it. By no means exhaustive, the ambition of this thesis is only to actively, effectively and directly contribute to the further research, development and implementation of note-taking in consecutive interpreting.

During the interpretation process, both memory and notes should be cultivated. While memory is of crucial to interpreters, notes can be of certain support. The importance of note-taking in consecutive interpreting had not been well recognized until Rozan laid down fundamental principles of note-taking in 1956 and Seleskovitch solidified the benefits of the skill in 1975. Experience has shown that the consecutive interpretation of speeches that are longer than two or three minutes requires at least some form of note-taking, of course, this also depends on the interpreter’s personal need, expertise and familiarity with the subject.

According to Jones (2002, p.39), note-taking is part of the whole process of consecutive interpreting including: understanding, analysis and re-expression, and if these activities “are not done correctly, the best notes in the world will not make a good interpreter”.

Jean-François Rozan (Rozan 1984) suggested seven steps to note taking which can be summarised in the following way:

Noting the idea rather than the word

Words alone can be often misleading, especially for interpreters because they have to produce a new version of a speech in a new language. The first thing to be noted should be main ideas. For the fact that the writing speed is always slower than speaking speed, it is impossible for the interpreter to write down everything spoken by the speaker. The interpreter is required to have the ability to identify, select and retain understanding of the original speech. Furthermore, by recording the main ideas in notes, the interpreter easily traces back the structure of the speech; hardly misses out important ideas; and always keeps fidelity to the original content.

Abbreviation. Unless the word is already short (4-5 letters), there should be a way to abbreviate words in order to make notes clearer. For example, if the interpreter wants to write “product” the word could be abbreviated as Prod., but this in itself can be confusing as it may also refer to the word “producer,” “production” or “productivity”.

Consequently, it is useful to conclude the last two letters of the word we are abbreviating as this is also helpful when maintaining gender and number consistency. There are many principles and rules for the use of abbreviations. However the most important one is that abbreviations must be consistent, if an interpreter has chosen “pop” standing for “popular” then he should find another abbreviation for “population”, for example, “pop on”. The following suggestions about creating abbreviations are based on the truth that the fewer strokes are written; the more time can be saved.

- Write what is heard: The interpreter can write a word by recording its sound only.

For example: high- hi; know- no; free- fre; fee- fe; night- nite; - Drop medial vowels:

For example: build- bld; legal- lgl; bulletin- bltn; save- sv; budget- bjt; - Write initial and final vowels:

For example: office- ofs; easy- ez; follow- flo; value- vlu; open- opn;

The rules of abbreviations set up by Rozan are classified into three categories: (i) abbreviation of words; (ii) abbreviation to indicate verb tenses and

(iii) abbreviating the register.

According to the first rule, “unless a word is short (4-5 letters), the interpreter should note it in an abbreviated form” and “write some of the first and last letters rather than trying to write as many letters as possible from the start onwards” (Rozan, n.d).

Links

It is essential to keep ideas and speech connected, and that should be represented in the interpreter’s notebook. Furthermore, the register of the speech should be maintained too, and that can be done by writing down specific words of the original speech. The ways in which ideas may be linked together are (i) the logical consequence which is expressed clearly with words such as consequently, as a result, accordingly or therefore; (ii) the logical cause which can be recognized with the words because, due to, as, or since; and opposition which often goes with but, yet, however or nevertheless (Jones, 2002, p.28-

29). Hardly does the interpreter get confused, if he or she notes links systematically. It is just liken to the act of marking road for each turn. Thanks to logical connections, the interpreter can follow every movement and direction change made by the speaker without any difficulty.

4.Symbols

Although the abbreviation is commonly used in notes, its most prominent drawback is that it tends to entice the interpreter to stick to the word level instead of meaning level. In other words, it easily leads the interpreter to think in terms of words rather than ideas, which could harm the interpretation. Therefore symbols are more preferable for their capacity of representing ideas and eliminating source language interference. A "symbol" is anything, a mark, sign or letter used to represent a thing or a concept.

Symbols are quicker and easier to write than words. Similar to abbreviations, firstly symbols need to be prepared in advance. Any symbol improvised in the middle of interpretation could drive the interpreter into a difficult and intense situation. One basic rule for the interpreter: only use the symbols which are already stuck in the mind. Secondly, symbols must be consistent. That means symbols are instantly associated for the interpreter himself with the meaning he gives them. Attending to this point, the interpreter can avoid mistakenly “deciphering” the meaning of the symbols he or she uses.

Followings are some symbol examples retrieved from electronic source at Interpreter Training Resource. Some could say that symbols clearly help the

interpreter take notes more quickly and effectively, and then it is wise to use as many symbols as possible. However, it would not seem rational to set up a rigidly unchanged rule for a degree of symbolization, each interpreter through practice would find their own balance. For some, symbolizing as much information as possible is good. For others, it is not necessary to do so.

To sum up, abbreviations and symbols are, like other elements in notes, “a means to an end, not an end in themselves” (Jones, 2002, p. 39). What is the use of abbreviations and symbols, if they do not help the interpreter to do his work better? For the interpreter to fully get benefits from note-taking, a system of abbreviations and symbols that is logical, connected and unequivocal should be developed on his or her own.

Country, nation, state = F al national (adjective) aly nationally ze to nationalize
ztn nationalisation o national (noun), citizen

Results and discussion. It is important to know that students tend to use symbols or abbreviate words because both symbols and abbreviations work differently in the notes. For some words or verbs, the use of symbols is recommendable. There are some ‘generic’ symbols that help learners to associate concepts to the ideas they caught while listening to the original speech. Moreover, symbols should be clear and unambiguous, so it is advisable to have the minimum number of symbols as possible to avoid confusing them with other symbols or even creating an excessive number of symbols. There is a tendency among learners to invent new symbols for almost everything, and most of the time, one symbol can summarize plenty of concepts. On the other hand, for long words and words that lead to confusion, it is advisable to abbreviate them in a way that does not confuse the student. For example, the word ‘recommendation’ is too long to write it in their notes. To make it shorter, it can be written like this: recomion. The purpose of abbreviating is saving as much time as possible because every stroke it is made takes valuable milliseconds that can be invested in following the original speech less overwhelmed.

In the process of note-taking, the interpreter is burden with making decisions all the time. When to take notes is a very important and also tough decision that requires the interpreter to arrive at properly and wisely. Interpreters should start the notes as soon as possible without having to wait for a complete “unit of meaning”. If he or she waits too long, there is danger of not being able to jot down sufficiently what has come earlier. Therefore, when the interpreter can sense the meaning of a sentence which might has not been

completed, he or she should note it down. Here the interpreter has the ability to “forecast” or “feel” upcoming things. Besides the interpreter is not required to take everything exactly the same way as the speaker, his or her notes are not presented in exact order as they were said by the speaker, so there is no need for the interpreter to wait until the speaker finishes an utterance to take note. It is also worth mentioning that as soon as speakers finish their utterance(s), the interpreter should stop taking notes instantly and start reproducing ideas. If the interpreter is too preoccupied with notes, he or she will delay the interpretation, which is not wanted. The interpreter cannot afford to take longer than the speaker. He or she is expected to react immediately after the speaker has finished.

CONCLUSION. In summary, this article tries to show that note taking is a very practical activity for consecutive interpretation. It is a discipline where the interpreter has to be constantly learning and training. One of the essential features of this area is the mastery of every language the interpreter is going to work with. A good note should give the main ideas of a speech, the links between those ideas, tenses of verbs figures, and numbers, lists of things, proper names, if mentioned, so as to relieve interpreters’ memory. A good note should also be as economical as possible with abbreviations and graphic symbols; then should be unequivocal and logical with diagonal layout, separating lines between ideas, and an useful left-hand margin. Which language used in notes and when to note are also important issues that should be taken into consideration by interpreters. Note taking has been proved to be very useful for the interpreter working consecutively. Firstly, notes improve concentration; prevent distraction, thus facilitating the reception and analysis of the speech. Secondly, notes help the interpreter relieve the memory. Although the interpreter may have understood the ideas of a speech, he or she cannot remember every point in the speech because one characteristic of short-term memory is that it only keeps information for a limited amount of time, cognitive scientists also show that for nearly all speakers of all languages peaks at around seven items, plus or minus two. By recording the specific details and data such as proper names, numbers, figures, lists of things, or specialized terms, technical expressions, notes release the interpreter from bearing the whole thing in mind. Thirdly, as mnemonic, notes activate the memory of the interpreter with cues or signals that call up the information in the speech. With notes, the main ideas, the secondary elements and the links among them become clear and easier for the interpreter to visualize. Finally, notes can also be used to

highlight missing details, inconsistencies within the speech and anything implausible that needs attention later. Thus notes play an important part in consecutive interpreting. However, taking proper notes needs a lot of practice, and the gap between the “theory of note-taking” and “actual notes” can be very large. In order to bridge the gap, first, an understanding of note-taking process is required.

Referances:

1. Abuín González, M. (2012). The language of consecutive interpreters' notes: Alexieva, Bistra (1994) “On teaching note-taking in consecutive interpreting”, 199–206.
2. Bahri, H. and Gholami, M. (2012). Handbook of interpreter training (HIT).Tehran: Rahnama Press
3. Blaszczyk, P. and Hanusiak, D. (2010). “The choice of language for notetaking for consecutive interpreting”
4. Dam, H. V. (2007). What makes interpreters' notes efficient? Features of
5. (non-) efficiency in interpreter's notes for consecutive interpreting
6. Gillies, A. (2005). Note-taking for Consecutive Interpreting: A Short Course
7. Dam, H.V. Consecutive interpreting, Y. Gambier and L. 2010.
8. Minjar-Beloručev, P.K. (1969)
9. Weber, W. (1989) “Improved ways of teaching consecutive interpretation”, in Laura Gran and John Dodds (eds), 161–166.
10. Albl-Mikasa, M. Sense in note-taking for consecutive interpreting, 2008
11. Bao, Chuanyun. 2015. Pedagogy. The Routledge handbook of interpreting, ed. HollyMikkelson, andRenéeJourdenais, 400–416. London: Routledge
12. D. Gile. – Lille: Presse Universitaire de Lille, 1995b. – 280 p.